

Oxidimetric Determination of Organic Derivatives of Hydrazine

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Hydrazine is a powerful reducing agent. Hydrazino group ($>N-N<$) in hydrazine and its derivatives is easily oxidised. Methods for the estimation of hydrazine and its derivatives are therefore based on quantitative oxidation of the hydrazino group by various oxidising agents under properly controlled conditions to avoid the occurrence of side reactions. Hydrazine on oxidation gives different end products, viz., nitrogen and ammonia, hydrogen azide and ammonia, or nitrogen only as oxidation products, depending on conditions of the reaction and type of oxidant used¹. Hofman and Kuspet² described the use of ammonium metavanadate as an oxidant for volumetric and nitrometric determination of hydrazine. Jamieson³ developed a visual method for the determination of hydrazine with potassium iodate in hydrochloric acid medium using chloroform as indicator. The organic layer, which was coloured pink due to iodine, became light pale yellow at the end point due to the formation of iodine monochloride. Roberto and Roncali⁴ observed quantitative oxidation of hydrazine with permanganate.

Kolthoff⁵ stated that best results were obtained when alkaline permanganate was used for the estimation of hydrazine. Chattaway⁶ studied the reaction of metallic oxides, permanganates, and chromates with several primary aromatic hydrazines, which on oxidation formed unstable hydroxyhydrazine. In presence of an alkali, this unstable compound immediately decomposed to a hydrocarbon, nitrogen, and water.

Browne and Shetterly⁷ studied the action of potassium persulphate, potassium permanganate, hydrogen peroxide, red lead, manganese dioxide, potassium perchlorate, sodium periodate, lead dioxide, potassium chlorate, potassium bromate, and potassium iodate in acid solution on hydrazine, and found that in most cases nitrogen and ammonia were the oxidation products. Datta and Choudhry⁸ studied the action of halogens and their oxyacid salts on semicarbazide hydrochloride, semioxamide and oxalyhydrazine in hydrochloric and sulphuric acid media. They estimated the

hydrazine derivatives by measuring the volume of nitrogen evolved during the reaction⁸. Ling and Nanji⁹ used iodine as an oxidising agent for the estimation of phenylhydrazine. Kurtenacker and Wagner¹⁰ estimated hydrazine in a mixture of hydroxylamine and hydrazine by oxidising the mixture with excess potassium bromate solution in presence of hydrochloric acid. Hydrazine present in the mixture was calculated from the volume of nitrogen gas evolved.

Gilbert¹¹ titrated hydrazine electrometrically with iodine in disodium phosphate buffer solution instead of sodium bicarbonate or sodium potassium tartrate, as recommended by earlier investigators. Kurtenacker and Kubina¹² described volumetric estimation of hydrazine and some of its derivatives with a standard solution of bromate and iodate in acid medium using indigo and chloroform as indicators respectively. Lang¹³ used potassium iodate in acid solution for the determination of hydrazine by adding potassium cyanide to the reaction mixture:

and titrating the iodine cyanide formed with sodium thiosulphate.

Hovorka¹⁴ proposed a new method for the determination of hydrazine and semicarbazide by oxidising them with excess potassium iodate in presence of mercuric perchlorate, which prevented liberation of iodine due to binding of iodide formed during the reaction. Komarowsky *et al.*¹⁵ have recommended the use of chloramine-T for direct volumetric estimation of hydrazine in presence of sodium bicarbonate and potassium iodide using starch as an indicator. Miller and Furman¹⁶ titrated phenylhydrazine and semicarbazide with potassium iodate in hydrochloric acid solution in presence of mercuric chloride to a potentiometric end point. Singh and Rehman¹⁷ used chloramine-T for potentiometric determination of hydrazine in acid solution. Szebelledy and Madis¹⁸ titrated hydrazine with potassium bromate in presence of phosphoric acid at 60-80°, using phosphomolybdic acid as redox indicator. Dernbach and Mehlig¹⁹ oxidised hydrazine sulphate with alkaline potassium ferricyanide; ferrocyanide formed was titrated with ceric sulphate in sulphuric acid medium. Vulterin and Zyka²⁰ determined hydrazine by direct potentiometric titration with potassium ferricyanide in alkaline medium.

McBride *et al.*²¹ carried out potentiometric titrations of a number of organic derivatives of hydrazine with potassium iodate in both hydrochloric and sulphuric acid media. They showed that each hydrazino group in monosubstituted hydrazines, their hydrazones, and acyl derivatives is oxidised with a four-electron change:

Singh *et al.*²² used potassium metaperiodate and chloramine-B in hydrochloric acid medium for potentiometric determination of hydrazine. They also used potassium metaperiodate as an oxidising agent for volumetric estimation of hydrazine sulphate and phenylhydrazine. Gottlieb²³ determined hydrazine with sodium hypobromite using the gasometric technique. Chalik *et al.*²⁴ used iodine monochloride in neutral or slightly acidic solution for potentiometric determination of thiosemicarbazide. They also used iodine monochloride for visual and potentiometric titrations in the estimation of hydrazine and phenyl-

hydrazine in sodium bicarbonate buffer. Issa and Issa²⁵ determined hydrazine indirectly by oxidising it with an excess of potassium permanganate in alkaline solution in presence of telluric acid. They carried out potentiometric titrations of hydrazine with potassium permanganate in presence of barium ions at varying concentrations of sodium hydroxide.

Litvineko *et al.*²⁶ carried out potentiometric titrations of carboxylic acid hydrazines and their hydrazones with sodium nitrite. Vulterin and Zyka²⁷ used sodium nitrite as volumetric reagent for the potentiometric determinations of hydrazine sulphate, semicarbazide hydrochloride, thiosemicarbazide, and phenylhydrazine hydrochloride in different acid media. Singh *et al.* have used chloramine-B²⁸, chloramine-T²⁹, potassium metaperiodate³⁰, sodium metavanadate³¹, diethylenetetra-ammonium sulphatocerate³², and sodium hypochlorite³³ as oxidants for determination of hydrazine in presence of hydrochloric acid using iodine monochloride-chloroform as indicator in visual titrations. McKennis *et al.*³⁴ carried out gasometric determination of hydrazine and its derivatives by using potassium iodate as an oxidant. Paul and Singh³⁵ have used potassium chlorite as volumetric reagent for the estimation of hydrazine sulphate. Schulek and Burger³⁶ employed bromine chloride for volumetric titrations of hydrazine and its derivatives using *p*-ethoxychry-sodine as an indicator.

Suseela³⁷ has estimated hydrazine by titrating it potentiometrically with alkaline potassium ferricyanide in presence of osmium tetroxide. Sant and Mukherji³⁸ have carried out amperometric titrations of hydrazine sulphate with potassium bromate using rotating platinum electrode. Berka and Zyka³⁹ have stated that in solution buffered with sodium bicarbonate, borate or sodium acetate, potassium metaperiodate can be titrated potentiometrically with hydrazine sulphate. Singh and Kashyap⁴⁰ have used iodine trichloride as a volumetric reagent for the determination of hydrazine sulphate in acid medium.

In this study some organic derivatives of hydrazine have been determined by a volumetric method using sodium vanadate⁴¹, chloramine-T⁴², potassium periodate⁴³, potassium bromate⁴⁴, sodium hypochlorite⁴⁵ and diethylenetetra-ammonium sulphatocerate⁴⁶ as oxidants.

Methods for the estimation of hydrazine and its derivatives are based on quantitative oxidation of hydrazino group present in each of the compounds. Although the hydrazino group is readily oxidised yet its quantitative oxidation is only effected under properly controlled conditions.

Oxidation of hydrazine has been a subject of critical study for the past fifty years or so. During this period several theories have been proposed by various investigators to explain the oxidation mechanism of hydrazine.

Browne *et al.*⁷ made a detailed study of the action of various oxidising agents on hydrazine in acid medium and formulated an oxidation mechanism to account for the formation of different oxidation products of hydrazine when different oxidants were used under similar conditions. Oxidising agents such as ferric, manganic, nickelic, cobaltic, cupric, and ceric ions oxidise hydrazine to nitrogen or to nitrogen and ammonia with one-electron change through the intermediate formation of tetrazane ($H_2N.NH.NH.NH_2$).

Oxidising agents such as persulphate, peroxide, chlorate, bromate, and molybdate ions oxidise hydrazine with two-electron change to hydrogen azide and ammonia through the intermediate formation of tetrazeno ($\text{H}_2\text{N}\cdot\text{N}=\text{N}\cdot\text{NH}_2$).

Permanganate, dichromate and iodate oxidise hydrazine to nitrogen with a four-electron change.

Abel⁴⁷ studied the action of permanganate and manganic ions on hydrazine and has put forward its oxidation mechanism with these oxidants. He assumed that hydrazine plays a dual role. It can either act as an electron donor ($\text{N}_2\text{H}_4 \rightarrow \text{NH}_2 + \text{NH}_2^\ddagger + e^-$) or act as an electron acceptor ($\text{N}_2\text{H}_4 + e^- \rightarrow \text{NH}_2^- + \text{NH}_2$). When it acts as an electron donor it is oxidised to nitrogen and when it acts as an electron acceptor, it is reduced to ammonia.

Higginson *et al.*⁴⁸ have discussed the classification of oxidising agents as two- or one-electron transfer reagents, depending on the products of their reaction with hydrazine. They stated that quantitative oxidation of hydrazine to nitrogen by two-electron transfer oxidants is in accord with the scheme in which N_2H_2 , once formed, can lead to nitrogen and not to ammonia. They explained the variable stoichiometry obtained

with one-electron transfer reagents due to two competing reactions which follow the initial formation of N_2H_3 .

Reaction (a) leads to a stoichiometry of 1 and (b) to stoichiometry of 4; so the stoichiometry for one-electron transfer reagents may lie between 1 and 4 depending on the proportion of these two reactions. They further stated that in alkaline medium one-electron transfer reagents produce only nitrogen quantitatively on oxidation of hydrazine by a four-electron change.

Higginson and Sutton⁴⁹ have also studied the mechanism of oxidation of hydrazine using ¹⁵N isotope as a tracer element. They showed that no N-N bond fission occurred and no new N-N bonds were formed when hydrazine was quantitatively oxidised to nitrogen.

McBride *et al.*²¹ have shown that nature and proportions of the end-products of the oxidation of hydrazine and its derivatives vary with the specific nature and the oxidation-reduction potential of the oxidising system, and with the pH of the medium.

Powell and Cahn⁵⁰, Higginson and Wright⁵¹, and Roseinsky⁵² have studied kinetics of the oxidation of hydrazine with ferric iron and proposed the following oxidation mechanism to account for the formation of nitrogen and ammonia as oxidation products.

In reaction (1) hydrazine is oxidised with one-electron change to nitrogen and ammonia and in reactions (2) and (3), oxidation of hydrazine to nitrogen takes place with a four-electron change. This is in agreement with the findings of Abel⁴⁷ and Higginson *et al.*⁴⁸.

Kolthoff *et al.*⁵³ have studied the mechanism of oxidation of hydrazine with ferric ethylenediamine tetra-acetate (FeY⁻) in borax and phosphate buffers with and without *ortho*-phenanthroline. They found that the oxidation product of hydrazine is mainly nitrogen. A very small amount of ammonia was formed in accord with the reaction ratio of 3.7 to 4.0 moles of FeY⁻ consumed per mole of hydrazine. They suggested the reaction mechanism, which is similar to that given by Powell and Cahn⁵⁰, Higginson and Wright⁵¹, and Roseinsky⁵², where N₂H₃ is supposed to be formed giving rise to nitrogen or to nitrogen and ammonia when hydrazine is oxidised.

In the investigations carried out by the present authors sodium vanadate, chloramine-T, potassium iodate, potassium bromate, sodium hypochlorite, and diethylenetetraammonium sulphatocerate were used to determine hydrazine and some of its organic derivatives in acid medium by an extraction end-point method or a potentiometric method. In case of potassium bromate, *p*-ethoxychrysodine was also used as an indicator. In case of potassium periodate a large amount of iodine was liberated during the titration, done

very carefully in presence of a large amount of hydrochloric acid to avoid the loss of the liberated iodine. In titrations with the other oxidants, a few c.c. of iodine monochloride were used as a catalyst and indicator. An advantage of using iodine monochloride over the conventional procedure in iodate and periodate titrations is that it does not involve liberation of large quantities of iodine with the subsequent risk of loss.

Although chloramine-T and sodium hypochlorite oxidised hydrazine and its derivatives instantaneously at low hydrochloric acid concentrations (2.0*N* to 5.0*N* and 2.0*N* to 2.5*N* in case of chloramine-T and sodium hypochlorite respectively), yet these reagents are not very suitable due to deterioration with time. These are to be prepared afresh and standardised when required for use. The titrations with diethylenetetra-ammonium sulphatocerate and sodium vanadate are done in hydrochloric acid medium of normality varying from 6.0*N* to 7.5*N*. Potassium bromate oxidises the organic derivatives of hydrazine at a faster rate than the sulphatocerate or sodium vanadate. Normality of hydrochloric acid is to be kept between 4.0*N* and 6.0*N* during the titration with potassium bromate when iodine monochloride is used as a catalyst and indicator. Moreover, potassium bromate is a primary standard in volumetric analysis.

It is found that the hydrazine derivative containing electrophilic groups, such as $>CO$ or $-NO_2$, retard the rate of oxidation by any of the oxidants used in this investigation. This effect is so dominating in case of dibenzoylhydrazine ($C_6H_5CO.NH.NH.COC_6H_5$) that it is rather difficult to oxidise it quantitatively. Although phenyl ($-C_6H_5$) group normally acts as an electron attracting group, yet it produces a positive inductomeric effect, *i.e.*, on demand by a reaction centre it can supply electrons. Hydrazine derivatives containing phenyl group are therefore very easily oxidised.

On the basis of the experimental results it can be stated that the organic derivatives of hydrazine are oxidised by a four-electron change per hydrazino group to nitrogen with the oxidants used in this investigation.

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